

The Tunisian thinker Ṭāhar al-Ḥaddād (1899-1935): life, work and legacy.

The aim of this doctoral thesis is to study the works of the Tunisian thinker Ṭāhar al-Ḥaddād (1899-1935) in order to analyze his thought, his ideology and his proposals, linking these elements with the socio-political and economic context of the colonial era in which he lived. Ṭāhar al-Ḥaddād is known as a nationalist, as well as a defender of the emancipation of women and the rights of workers. Throughout his life, he wrote two complete and one incomplete books, a collection of aphorisms, several newspaper articles and numerous poems, as well as a Qur'ānic commentary that remains unpublished. Of all his contributions, the first two that we have mentioned have been the ones that have received the most attention from the academic world, which began to rescue his legacy from the seventies onwards. In his lifetime, both works were highly controversial, drawing fierce criticism from the Dustūr party, the settlers, and Tunisia's conservative religious elite.

This thesis is divided into ten chapters, the first of which is a presentation. The second chapter sets out the objectives, the theoretical framework and the methodology that we have employed. The third one corresponds to the state of the art, while chapters four and five comprise an overview of the historical, political, social and economic circumstances that were key for al-Ḥaddād and his production. The sixth chapter analyzes his biography and his thinking, as well as the most notorious influences present in his works. Chapter seven delves into his minor works, while chapters eight and nine are devoted to his major ones. The last chapter collects the conclusions that can be drawn from our research. To facilitate condensing the information, this summary will incorporate aspects of the context, biography, thought and influences received by the author as it analyzes his works, in such a way as to offer an integrated and not segmented, view of the thesis.

Our main objective is, therefore, to analyze all his works in order to have a vision of his production as a whole and to establish links between all the themes and formats that he employed. This will allow us to determine which issues were most important to the author, why he chose different platforms to write each work or what ideological elements supported his compositions. Our methodology will be, on the one hand, the

study of original works in Arabic and, on the other hand, the use of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) as an analysis tool. The latter will facilitate the location of the ideological elements that we mentioned earlier, which, in turn, will offer us the necessary perspective to align the author with the cultural, political and intellectual environment of his time. Regarding the theoretical framework, we will be basing our research on theories such as orientalism, post-orientalism and decolonial and subaltern studies. Being a colonized subject and one in which numerous matrixes of domination converged, al-Ḥaddād was clearly a subaltern subject who was fully aware of it.

All of this leads us to a primary need, which is to locate the historical context of colonial Tunisia and, specifically, the political and cultural milieu in which al-Ḥaddād was involved. Being an author closely linked to the social events of his time, his work cannot be fully understood if the situation in the country is not taken into account at all times, since most of his production was generated in response to situations of discrimination or injustice that occurred in the day to day and drew his attention. Perhaps the key is to understand the struggle that was taking place in the country between settlers and the native population and how it was being channeled through various platforms. The better-known of all of them was the Dustūr party, although it was more autonomous than independent, of which the author became a member from its very foundation (in 1920).

Part of this thesis is devoted to determining some biographical aspects of the author, which are not always obvious. Al-Ḥaddād was born in the capital Tunis in 1899 (although some sources cite other dates, this is confirmed by his brother) and belonged to a middle-class family. His father was a poultry seller in one of the city's souks, and his mother, of whom little is known, was illiterate. He had several siblings of whom only one survived. He studied at al-Zaytūna after attending the *kuttāb* and graduated with a basic diploma called *taṭwī*¹. Not long after that, he was employed as accountant in a local charity for some time, but later left it to devote himself entirely to social reform. Shortly before he joined the Dustūr, al-Ḥaddād had been publishing newspaper articles on nationalist issues, but his activity intensified after entering the party. In 1924, his contributions to the problematic Law of Naturalization, promulgated in December 1923, nearly monopolized all of his journalistic production during that date. Al-Ḥaddād harshly criticized not only the law or its adherents, but also the spirit that had fostered it. In this regard, he argued that the true interest of the French was to dilute the Tunisian identity, gradually turning it into "French", to eliminate any attempt at independence and to ensure

the loyalty of the colonized to the metropolis. In doing so, he demonstrated that he was fully aware of the ins and outs of the colonial system and his status as a subordinate subject.

Regarding his work, we can distinguish two major categories: minor works, formed by a *dīwān*, newspaper articles, *al-Ta‘alīm al-islamī wa-ḥarakat al-iṣlāḥ fī yāma‘ al-Zaytūna* (*Islamic education and the reform movement at al-Zaytūna mosque*) and *Jawāṭir* (*Thoughts*), a collection of aphorisms; and his two major works, entitled *Al-'ummāl al-tūnisīyyūn wa-zuhūr al-ḥaraka al-niqābiyya* (*Tunisian workers and the rise of trade unionism*) and *Imrā'tu-nā fī l-ṣarī'a wa-l-mu'ytama'* (*Our woman in Islamic law and society*).

Al-Ḥaddād contributed poems to the literary journals of the time, most of which dealt mainly with nationalist themes or social criticism, with some exceptions of lyrical content that is easy to interpret as feelings awakened in the author by the socio-political situation he was experiencing. These poems are usually considered as circumstantial, that is, they are not the fruit of the author's express interest in cultivating himself as a poet, but rather that he used poetry as a platform to spread his messages of social change among readers. In fact, some researchers have even pointed out the inspiration of al-Ḥaddād in other poets of the time, indicating that the author in question was rather an 'amateur poet'. He demonstrated with his poems his early interest in social reform, as well as a keen eye to analyze the circumstances of his environment, locate problems and offer solutions.

As an example of this, during his time as a student at the great al-Zaytūna mosque, he began writing *al-Ta‘alīm*, whose objective was to contribute to the movement for educational reform. In it, he analyzed the history of the institution, its situation at the time from the perspective of the student body, as well as the problems derived from the scarce updating of the teaching methodology and the educational curriculum. Although he did not complete it, the book constitutes a reference of great interest for the study of the institution, as well as on the very active student movement in colonial Tunisia.

Al-Ta‘alīm is one of the author's works that was published posthumously. The other one was *Jawāṭir*, which briefly collects al-Ḥaddād's opinion on topics as varied as democracy, independence, female emancipation or capitalism. It is the last one that he wrote and, since it was not intended to be published, in it we find his sharpest opinions on these delicate matters. In addition, it is especially interesting because, when comparing

his contributions on topics such as feminism or trade unionism with those that he included in his other works, we see that an evolution took place and that *Jawāfir* is a reflection of the maturity of his ideas and of curation of his thought. In fact, some of the issues he dealt with in this work are absent from the others or appear only in a veiled and superficial way.

As for his major works, the first was *al-'Ummāl*, dedicated to the trade union question. Due to his friendship with key figures of the labor movement in the country, such as Muḥammad 'Alī al-Ḥammī, and his own personal experience as the son of a vendor in the souk, al-Ḥaddād always had the lives of those who belonged to the working class very much in mind. Social injustices, added to economic ones and colonialism, were a great obstacle for the majority of the Tunisian population of the time, who belonged to this class. For this reason, al-Ḥaddād collaborated with al-Ḥammī and other colleagues in devising an economic cooperative whose objective was to distribute consumer goods to the poorest workers. This project never saw the light of day as the outbreak of some historic strikes in Tunis, Bizerte and the surrounding areas modified the original plans.

This book responds directly to its historical context. In 1924, a massive strike took place among the porters of the Tunisian port and gradually spread to other cities and industries in the country. The lack of cooperation on the part of the French trade union center, the Confédération Générale du Travail (CGT), and the police repression suffered by the strikers led al-Ḥammī, al-Ḥaddād and the rest of those who wanted to found the cooperative to rethink the project as something more meaningful. Thus, they decided to help organize the demonstrations and support the strike committees to achieve their objectives. Little by little, they forged the idea of founding an autonomous Tunisian trade union center, which was not under the scope of the CGT and, therefore, was outside the colonial ideology that permeated the previous one and about which native trade unionists complained often.

Al-Ḥammī recruited various personalities from Tunisian trade unionism into the ranks of this new central, which was called the Confédération Générale des Travailleurs Tunisiens (CGTT), as well as al-Ḥaddād. The latter held the post of chief of propaganda, for which he wrote numerous newspaper articles. However, the founding of a central that was not controlled by the French was a clash between European trade unionists and Tunisian nationalists and, more specifically, between Joachim Durel (CGT) and al-Ḥammī (CGTT). Due to friction between both sides and the ideological and strategic

position of the Dustūr, the party opposed the founding of the CGTT, which prompted al-Ḥaddād to leave it. In addition, the Dustūr, together with the French central, harassed the members of the CGTT, especially its founders, through a campaign that sought to turn public opinion against them. All this, added to the accusation that the CGTT was a nationalist body that promoted a plot against France and that promoted racism and religious sectarianism, served as a pretext for the colonial authorities to intervene and imprison or exile the majority of its leaders. Of the founding members, the only one who escaped such a fate was precisely al-Ḥaddād, although the reasons why remain unclear.

As a way to restore his comrades' honor, as well as to reveal the truth behind the political ins and outs of the French confederation and the Dustūr, al-Ḥaddād wrote *al-Ummāl* in 1927. Although it was only in circulation for a short time, since it was censored by the French authorities, the work is key to understanding the economic environment of the time, as well as the most notable events of the trade unionist scene of the 1920s in Tunisia. The work addresses important issues such as the chronicles of the strikes in Tunisia and Bizerte, the difference between wages and the cost of living in the country or the true involvement of the CGTT with the nationalist movement. At the same time, it gives an account of the influence of socialist and Marxist ideologies on the author's thought, with references to Karl Marx, among others.

The harsh repression suffered by the trade union center led to its almost immediate dismantling, so al-Ḥaddād focused his efforts on another aspect of social reform: female emancipation. Aware of the advances in this matter that were taking place in neighboring countries, al-Ḥaddād entered the Law School and began to write a monographic work dedicated to the issue, *Imrā'tu-nā*, which would quickly become his best-known book, as well as the most controversial one. The work is divided into two parts, the first of which focuses on legal issues that discriminated against women and that, in his opinion, were mainly due to biased interpretations of the Qur'ānic and prophetic message. Issues such as the essence of women in Islam as believers and as members of humanity, inheritance, marriage and its dissolution, polygyny or seclusion are discussed here, and the author's most innovative proposals are collected, such as the prohibition of polygyny and the need to reform inheritance laws to make them equal between men and women. It follows in the footsteps previously left by authors such as Muḥammad 'Abduh, whom al-Ḥaddād admired, which in some way makes it possible to link the author's thinking with the Islamic reformism movement (*salafiyya*). This first section closes with the opinion of

several '*ulamā*' of different legal schools to whom al-Ḥaddād sent questions related to its contents, imitating the style of one of the key works of Jayr al-Dīn al-Tūnisī, of whom he considered himself an admirer. '*Ulamā*' such as al-Jaṭṭāb Bušnāq, Ibn 'Āšūr and Bayram VI, of great prestige in their time, participated in this section. Collecting their answers, which showed great discrepancies both between different legal schools and often even within the same one, allowed the author to demonstrate to his readers that there was no unanimity on most issues and that, therefore, the Qur'ān could be open to different interpretations: one of which was his own.

The second half is devoted to social and cultural aspects involving various types of discrimination against women, such as the lack of options to educate Muslim girls, traditions around dowry, childrearing, the authority at home or the debate surrounding which spouse the housework should fall on. The book was published in 1930, but it was quickly withdrawn from circulation by the French authorities, who gave in to the insistence of Tunisia's more conservative religious elite. In addition to the political reasons behind this rejection, it is clear that the book, which questioned a good part of the social foundations of Islam in the country, was widely rejected and harshly criticized by the most conservative sectors. Various al-Zaytūna '*ulamā*' and professors published pamphlets, newspaper articles, and even entire books to criticize and refute al-Ḥaddād's proposals on female emancipation. In a short time, the situation took on a personal face and the criticism turned into personal attacks and a campaign of harassment against the author that ended up confining him in his home, both from fear of physical attacks and for health reasons. He was prevented from taking the Law School graduation exam and his *taṭwī*' was also confiscated (although there is controversy over this last point because his brother denied it in an interview). The stress he was subjected to during the time, added, perhaps, to previous conditions, caused his health to deteriorate until his death a few years later, in 1935. Tuberculosis is often referred to as the cause of his death, although he also suffered from cardiovascular problems that could have aggravated the situation.